

Short communication

Two new records of the subfamily Xoridinae (Hym.: Ichneumonidae) from Mazandaran province, Iran

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چکیده

گونه‌های *X. (Xorides) gravenhorstii* (Curtis) و *Xorides (Xorides) fuligator* (Thunberg) برای اولین بار از ایران، استان مازندران گزارش می‌شوند. بنابراین، تعداد گونه‌های گزارش شده از زیرخانواده Xoridinae از ایران به سه گونه افزایش می‌یابد.

The subfamily Xoridinae (Hym.: Ichneumonidae) comprises about 204 species in four genera (Yu *et al.*, 2012). The genus *Xorides* Latreille, with 147 species, is the most diverse genus in this subfamily and divided into eight subgenera (Townes, 1969; Kasparyan, 1981; Yu *et al.*, 2012). The members of this subfamily are known as larval parasitoids of the beetles of the families Anobiidae, Buprestidae, Buprestidae, Cerambycidae (Kasparyan, 1981). Only the species *Xorides (Gonophonus) corcyrensis* Kriechbaumer, reared from the Rosaceae twig borer, *Ospherantheria coerulea* Redtenbacher (Col.: Cerambycidae), has been recorded from Iran (Radjabi, 1991; Barahoei *et al.*, 2012; Hooshyar *et al.*, 2012; Mohammadi-Khoramabadi, 2013). Here, we record further two species of the subfamily Xoridinae from Iran. The specimens were collected using sweep net during 2011 and reared in 2014. They are deposited in the insect collection of the College of Agriculture and Natural Resources of Darab, affiliated to Shiraz University.

- *Xorides (Gonophonus) Förster, 1869*

This subgenus can be identified by the following characters: vein 1cu-a in forewing basad of vein M + Rs (basal vein); areolet with vein 2rs-m as long as vein 2M; posterior transverse carina of mesosternum complete; first metasomal tergite with a post median strong transverse reticulate-wrinkled groove; body coarsely punctured and 4th segment of maxillary palp not shortened (Townes, 1969; Kasparyan, 1981).

- *Xorides (Gonophonus) corcyrensis* Kriechbaumer, 1894

Material examined – IRAN, Yazd province: 1 ♂, Abarkouh, N 31°12', E 53°28', 1510 m a.s.l., 3.iv.2014, ex: *O. coerulea*.

Diagnosis – Metasoma completely black; antenna lacking white ring, pterostigma black, basally white (Kasparyan, 1981).

Distribution – Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Greece, Iran, Italy, Russia (Radjabi, 1991; Yu *et al.*, 2012).

- *Xorides (Xorides) Latreille, 1809*

This subgenus is characterized by the following characters: vein 1cu-a in the forewing distad of the vein M + Rs (basal vein); areolet with vein 2rs-m strongly smaller than vein 2M; first metasomal tergite without a post median strong transverse reticulate-wrinkled groove or lateral groove; body not coarsely punctured; trochantellus of fore and mid legs without apical teeth; 4th segment of maxillary palpus shortened (Townes, 1969; Kasparyan, 1981).

- *Xorides (Xorides) fuligator* (Thunberg, 1824)

Material examined – IRAN, Mazandaran province: 1 ♀, 1 ♂, Nour, N 36°21', E 52°06', 692 m a.s.l., 23.vi.2011, sweeping.

Diagnosis – This species is distinguished from other related species by apically filiform antenna; lacking striate temple; red metasoma; basally swollen fore and mid tibiae, and depression in anterior half; and shiny hind coxa (Kasparyan, 1981).

Distribution – Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom, former Yugoslavia (Yu *et al.*, 2012). New to Iran.

- *Xorides (Xorides) gravenhorstii* (Curtis, 1831)

Material examined – IRAN, Mazandaran province: 1 ♀, Nour, N 36°21', E 52°06', 692 m a.s.l., 23.vi.2011, sweeping.

Diagnosis – This species can be separated from other species of the genus by apically distinct clavate antenna; densely striate temple and red metasoma (Kasparyan, 1981).

Distribution – Algeria, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, former Czechoslovakia, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, The Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom, former Yugoslavia (Yu *et al.*, 2012). New to Iran.

References

- Barahoei, H., Rakhshani, E. & Riedel, M.** (2012) A checklist of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from Iran. *Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics* 8, 83-132.
- Hooshyar, H., Vafaei-Shoushtari, R. & Barimai-Varandi, H.** (2012) Faunistic study of Ichneumon wasps, (Hym., Ichneumonidae) from Mazandaran province, Iran. *Proceedings of the 20th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, Vol. I, Pests*, p. 224.
- Kasparyan, D. R.** (1981) *Opredelitel nasekomie evropeiskie casti USSR. Preponcatokrilie*. Part III, 688 pp. Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences.
- Mohammadi-Khoramabadi, A.** (2013) Identification and determination of species diversity of parasitoid wasps of the Pimpliformes group (Hym.: Ichneumonidae) in central north of Iran. Ph. D. Thesis. Tarbiat Modares University, 315 pp .
- Radjahi, Gh.** (1991) *Insects attacking resaceous fruit trees in Iran (Coleoptera)*. Vol. 1, 2nd ed. 221 pp. Plant Pests and Disease Research Institute.
- Townes, H.** (1969) The genera of Ichneumonidae, part 1. *Memoirs of the American Entomological Institute* 11, 1-300 .
- Yu, D. S., van Achterberg, K. & Horstmann, K.** (2012) World Ichneumonidae 2011; taxonomy, biology, morphology and distribution. Available from: www.taxapad.com (accessed 20 August 2014).

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